

Polynuclear Aromatic Hydrocarbons. Part VIII. Synthesis of 6-Methyl-1,2-benzotetraphene

R. N. Handa, K. S. Sharma and S. M. Mukherji

Synthesis of 6-methyl-1,2-benzotetraphene through the Colonge-Mukherji cyclialkylation/cyclodehydration of tetralin with 2-allyl-1-tetralone is described.

Pullman¹ reported that 1,2-benzotetraphene (2:3, 5:6-dibenzphenanthrene), which was first prepared by Hewett², is bereft of carcinogenic activity. Literature³⁻⁵ records instances of methyl homologues having considerable carcinogenic activity even when the parent hydrocarbon is devoid of it. The classical example of 1,2-benzanthracene and 4-methyl-1,2-benzanthracene may be cited in this context⁵. Therefore, in spite of Pullman's findings, it was thought worthwhile to make available a suitably substituted methyl homologue of 1,2-benzotetraphene which may eventually be tested for biological activity. No methyl homologue seems to have been synthesized and tested for carcinogenicity. However, recently Mukherji and Sharma⁶ have synthesized 3-methyl-, and 3,6-dimethyl-1,2-benzotetraphene through the sequence of Colonge-Mukherji cyclialkylation/cyclodehydration method. This method is now extended to the synthesis of 6-methyl-1, 2-benzotetraphene. Special interest attaches to this structure as this contains both 1,2-benzanthracene and 3,4-benzphenanthrene moieties, which, by themselves, are already proved to have great potency as carcinogens. The present method has been developed on the model of the synthesis of 9-methylphenanthrene by Mukherji and Bhattacharyya⁷, the starting material being 2-allyl tetralone-1, prepared according to the conditions of Mukherji *et al.*⁸

Pure tetralin was condensed with 2-allyl-tetralone-1 in the presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride by employing the conditions reported by Vig *et al.*⁹.

The ketone (I) was reduced by Meerwein-Ponndorf method to the alcohol (II), which underwent smooth cyclisation with concentrated H₂SO₄ to give 6-methyl-3,

1. Pullman, *Compt. rend.*, 1953 **236**, 2318.
2. Hewett, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 1286.
3. Shear and Leiter, *J. Natl. Cancer Inst.*, 1941, **2**, 241; Shear, *Am. J. Cancer.*, 1938, **33**, 499; Shear, Leiter and Perrault, *J. Natl. Cancer Inst.*, 1940, **1**, 303, 323.
4. Berenblum, *Cancer Research*, 1945, **5**, 263; Beckmann, Cook *et al.*, *Proc. Roy. Soc. (London)*, 1937, **B-123**, 343; Badger, Cook *et al.*, *Proc. Roy. Soc. (London)*, 1940, **B-129**, 439; Bachmann, Kennaway, *Yale. J. Biol. Med.*, 1938, **11**, 97; *Chem. Abstr.*, 1939, **33**, 2204; Shabad and Kleinsberg, *Byull. Eksp. Biol. Med.*, 1944, **17**, No. 6, 57; *Chem. Abstr.*, 1945, **39**, 5316.
5. Badger, *Nat. Cancer Inst. Monograph* 1962, No 9, p.1.
6. Sharma, Ph. D. Thesis, The University, Kurukshetra, 1965.
7. Mukherji and Bhattacharyya, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1952, **17**, 1202.
8. Mukherji, Gaiind and Rao, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1954, **19**, 328.
9. Vig, Kessar, Kubba and Mukherji, *J. Ind. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **32**, 697.

4, 4a, 5, 6, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12b-decahydro-1,2-benzotetrapheno (III) in 70% yield. The elemental analysis of the carbinol (II) gave a rather higher value for carbon possibly

due to partial dehydration during distillation. The dehydrogenation of the hydroaromatic system (III) was readily effected with palladiumcharcoal (30%) to give 6-methyl-1,2-benzotetraphene in excellent yield (70%), m.p. 83-84°.

The ketone (I) was also cyclodehydrated with polyphosphoric acid to 3,4,5,6,8,9,10,11-octahydro-1,2-benzotetraphene following the conditions of Djerassi *et al.*¹⁰. The hydroaromatic compound was then smoothly aromatized (as mentioned above) to obtain 6-methyl-1,2-benzotetraphene (IV).

However the compound did not furnish a solid picrate.

EXPERIMENTAL*

2-(β(6'-Tetra-lyl)-propyl)-tetralone-1 (I).—To the stirred pure dry tetralin (100 ml.), at 0° and protected from moisture, was added aluminium chloride (3 g., out of a total of 12 g.) followed by dropwise addition of 2-allyl-1-tetralone (from the total of 7.5 g.) till the temperature reached 5°. Addition was discontinued at this stage, while stirring continued. When the temperature reached 0°, anhydrous aluminium chloride (3 g.) was again added

10. Djerassi *et al.*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1957, 22, 393.

*B.P.S. and M.P.S. are uncorrected.

followed by dropwise addition of allyl ketone, the procedure repeated. The mixture was stirred for 5 hr. at 0-5°, after the completion of addition, when it developed a cherry red colour. Thereafter, the complex was poured on to iced hydrochloric acid, with stirring. The organic layer was separated, the aqueous layer extracted with two 50 ml. portions of ether, the combined extracts washed with dilute hydrochloric acid, then with water, 5% sodium bicarbonate solution, and finally with water and dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate. After removal of the solvent and distillation in vacuum, this yielded 8.5 g. (86%) of a viscous oily product, b.p. 220-25°/3 mm. (Found: C, 87.24; H, 7.86. Calc. for $C_{23}H_{16}O$: C, 86.79; H, 8.17%).

6-Methyl-3,4, 4a, 5,6,8,9,10,11,12b-decahydro-1,2-benzotetraphene (III).—2-(β (6-Tetra-allyl-propyl)-tetralol-1 (II).—The above ketone (I; 4 g.) was reduced to the corresponding carbinol with aluminium isopropoxide, prepared from 2.5 g. of aluminium and 75 ml. of isopropyl alcohol, according to the standard procedure. The reaction mixture after being worked up in the usual way, was distilled and gave 86% yield of the carbinol(II), b.p. 217-20°/4 mm. (Found: C, 88.14; H, 9.17. Calc. for $C_{23}H_{28}O$: C, 86.2; H, 8.7%).

The carbinol (II; 3g.) was cooled in an ice-bath, 2.5 ml. of conc. H_2SO_4 (sp. gr. 1.84) was added, and the contents were mixed intimately. After 3 hr. the reaction mixture was diluted with water, and worked up in the usual way. On distillation in vacuum there was obtained 2 g. (70%) of a gummy product, b.p. 215-17°/3mm. (Found: C, 91.31; H, 8.67. Calc. for $C_{13}H_{16}$: C, 91.40; H, 8.60%).

6-Methyl-1,2-benzotetraphene (IV).—The decahydrocompound (III; 1.8 g.) was smoothly aromatized by heating with palladium charcoal (30%; 2 g.) at 320-40° for 5 hr. in the atmosphere of carbon dioxide. Thereafter, the mixture was extracted with ether, filtered and the solvent removed, and was thus obtained a light yellow solid, 1.2g. (69%). It was crystallized from benzenepetroleum (40-60°) mixture in light yellow leaflets, m.p. 83-84°. (Found: C, 95.13; H, 5.66. $C_{23}H_{16}$ requires C, 94.52; H, 5.48%).

6-Methyl-1, 2-benzotetraphene(IV) [by cyclodehydration of the ketone (I)].—The ketone (I; 3.5 g.) was treated with phosphoric acid (24 ml.) and phosphorous pentoxide(32 g.), and heated with stirring for 3 hr. on a steam bath and for an additional 4 hr. at 165° in an oil bath. After cooling the contents to room temperature, ice-cold water (300 ml.) was added, the organic material taken up in ether, aqueous layer extracted thrice with 20 ml. portions of ether and the combined ether extracts were washed free from acid. After drying over anhydrous magnesium sulphate, the solvent was removed. The crude product was dissolved in 50 ml. of absolute alcohol, 5 ml. of glacial acetic acid, and 5 g. of Girard's Reagent-T and refluxed for 2 hr. Thereafter, 300 ml. of water containing 3 g. of sodium hydroxide was added and the mixture extracted with ether (50 ml. portions) five times. The combined ether layers washed free from acid and alkali and dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate. After removal of the solvent and distillation under reduced pressure, a viscous product was collected, 2.5 g. (75%), which boiled at 205-207°/2 mm.

The above cyclised product (2 g) was dehydrogenated as before to obtain a light yellow coloured solid, 1.4 g. (70%). It was crystallized from benzene petroleum ether

(40-60°) mixture in light yellow leaflets, m.p. 83-84°. (Mixture m.p. with the earlier sample remained undepressed).

I.R. Absorption:— 2950, 1650, 1600, 1480, 1450, 1375, 1330, 1280, 1210, 1170, 1125,
(NUJOL) 1090, 1030, 1020, 1005, 965, 955, 915, 890, 875, 860, 825, 800, 780,
745, 735, 720, 700 cm^{-1} .

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
KURUKSHETRA UNIVERSITY,
KURUKSHETRA.

Received March 1, 1966.